

DERIVATION OF TROUTON'S RULE

BY M. S. TELANG

Various methods of deriving Trouton's rule are reviewed and a new method of derivation is proposed.

Trouton (*Phil. Mag.*, 1884, *v*, 18, 54) pointed out an interesting and important relation between the latent heat of vaporisation (l) of a substance and its absolute boiling point (T_b) under a pressure of one atmosphere and this has come to be known as Trouton's rule.

$$\frac{Ml}{T_b} = \frac{\Delta H}{T_b} = \text{constant} \quad \dots (1)$$

where M is the molecular weight. This relation may also be considered as expressing the constancy of the entropy of vaporisation under the conditions mentioned. However, this rule is only approximately true and when applied to liquids with a wide range of boiling points, the constant shows a distinct deviation. Yet, this empirical rule is an approximation of considerable usefulness when approximate data are needed.

Many modifications of Trouton's rule have been proposed from time to time. Each of these modifications brings only some types of compounds into better agreement than what is obtained with the original Trouton's rule. The one that deserves greatest consideration is that due to Hildebrand (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, *37*, 970).

A Review of the Methods of Derivation of Trouton's Rule

(i) By integrating the Clausius-Clapeyron equation, we have

$$\ln p = - \frac{\Delta H}{RT} + I \quad \dots (2)$$

neglecting the change in ΔH . This equation leads to Trouton's rule for the relation between the heat of vaporisation and the boiling point when $p=1$ atmos., the value of I for a majority of liquids being nearly 11, which gives

$$\frac{\Delta H}{T_b} = 22$$

at the boiling point (Rodebush and Webb, "Taylor's Treatise on Physical Chemistry", Mac-Millan & Co., London, 1931, p. 1385).

(ii) Cederberg (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1911, *77*, 498) derived an equation for calculating Trouton coefficients from critical constants. Thus

$$\frac{\Delta H}{T_b} = \frac{R \ln p_c (1 - 1/p_c)}{1 - \frac{T_b}{T_c}} \quad \dots (3)$$

where the critical pressure (p_c) is expressed in atmospheres (*cf.* Taylor "Treatise on Physical Chemistry", p. 299). Guldberg (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1890, *5*, 374) has indicated that for a large number of normal substances, the absolute boiling point is approximately 0.66 of the critical temperature. Hence, for normal substances, the variation of Trouton's constant is expected to be due to the corresponding variations of p_c . However, the values of Trouton's coefficients calculated according to this equation are in fair agreement with the experimental values.

(iii) The following equation represents the relation between the relative change in the concentration of the saturated vapour and the energy of vaporisation (ΔE) i. e. internal latent heat of vaporisation (Brönsted, "Physical Chemistry", William Heinemann, London, 1937, p. 52).

$$\Delta H - RT = RT^2 \frac{d \ln C}{dT} \text{ or } \Delta E = RT^2 \frac{d \ln C}{dT} \quad \dots (4)$$

From the kinetic theory, it can easily be shown that during the transition from liquid to vapour (*idem, ibid*, p. 82),

$$\frac{N_1}{N_0} = e^{-E_{ca}/kT} \quad \dots (5)$$

where N_0 and N_1 represent the number of molecules per c.c. in the vapour and liquid respectively, E_{ca} , is the critical energy which liquid molecules must possess in order to penetrate the surface of the liquid and k is the Boltzmann constant. Further,

$$\frac{N_1}{N_0} = \frac{V_0}{V_1}$$

where V_0 and V_1 are the molar volumes of the vapour and liquid respectively. If these volumes are corrected for the volume occupied by the molecules themselves, then

$$\frac{N_1}{N_0} = \frac{V_0 - b}{V_1 - b} = e^{-E_{ca}/kT} \quad \dots (6)$$

where b is the Van der Waals' constant. This equation (6) gives better agreement with experimental values. By differentiating the above equation with respect to temperature,

$$E_{ca} = kT^2 \frac{d \ln N_0}{dT} = \frac{R}{N} T^2 \frac{d \ln N_0}{dT} \quad \dots (7)$$

This equation is identical with the thermodynamic vaporisation equation (4), if ΔE is put equal to NE_{ca} , where N is the Avogadro number. It follows, therefore, that the heat of vaporisation should be identified with the increase of potential energy, which the molecules undergo when they pass from the liquid to the vapour through the surface field of force. Equation (5) predicts that the ratio between the concentrations of molecules in the vapour and in the liquid should be depending only on E_{ca}/T , which Trouton discovered from his experimental observations only.

Equation (6) may be written as

$$\Delta E = \Delta H - RT = RT \ln \frac{V_0 - b}{V_1 - b} = RT \ln \frac{N_1}{N_0}$$

or $\frac{\Delta H}{T} = R \left(1 + \ln \frac{N_1}{N_0} \right)$

Hence at the boiling point,

$$\frac{\Delta H}{T_b} = R \left(1 + \ln \frac{N_1}{N_0} \right) \quad \dots (8)$$

This relation (8) has also been deduced from partition functions of liquids (*vide* Butler, *Chem. Soc. Ann. Report*, 1937, 34, 78, *et. seq.*). By employing the partition function of Fowler and Darwin, for a perfect gas, this function is

$$f_0 = (2\pi mkT)^{\frac{3}{2}} V b(T) / N h^3 \quad \dots (9)$$

where $b(T)$ is that part of the whole partition function which is dependent upon the vibrational and rotational energy of the molecule. Further, on the assumption that the vibrational and rotational states are the same in the liquid as in the gas, Eyring *et al.* (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1937, 33, 73; *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1937, 41, 249) give the following expression for the partition function of a liquid

$$f_1 = V, \frac{(2\pi mkT)^{\frac{3}{2}}}{h^3} b(T) \exp. (\Delta E / RT) \quad \dots (10)$$

where V/N is equal to V_r , the free volume of the liquid. Correlating (9) and (10), and taking logarithms

$$\frac{\Delta E}{T} = R \ln \frac{V_0}{V_r}$$

Hence, the entropy of vaporization of a liquid is

$$\Delta = S \frac{\Delta H}{T_b} = \frac{\Delta E}{T_b} + R = R \left(1 + \ln \frac{V_0}{V} \right) \quad \dots (11)$$

which is the same as (8). From Trouton's rule, it is already known that $\Delta H/T_b$ is constant for normal liquids at their boiling points. Hildebrand (*loc. cit.*) showed that a better constancy was found when liquids were compared at temperatures at which they give rise to equal vapour concentrations. Under such conditions, V_0 is constant and hence from equation (11) it follows that the free space in the liquid is also constant. It has been indicated by Eyring (*J. Chem. Phys.*, 1936, 4, 283) that, since the energy required to make a hole in a liquid is the same as that needed to remove a molecule from the liquid, the concentration of holes in the liquid must be evidently equal to the concentration of molecules in the vapour. At equal vapour concentrations, liquids will therefore have equal "concentrations of holes"; in combination with (11) this leads to a simple interpretation of Trouton's rule. When the molecular rotations are not fully developed in the liquid, as in the case of associated liquids in which directed bonds occur, the entropy of vaporisation will be greater than in (11), which is already known from experimental observations.

Proposed Method of Derivation of Trouton's Rule.

Sugden (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 1781) has given a relation between density and temperature as

$$D - d = D_0 (1 - T_r)^{\frac{3}{2}} \quad \dots (12)$$

where D and d are the densities of liquid and vapour respectively, D_0 is the density of the supercooled liquid at absolute zero and T_r is the reduced temperature. Neglecting d , which is usually small at the boiling point, equation (12) may be written as

$$D = D_0 (1 - T_r)^{\frac{3}{2}}$$

$$\text{Hence } \frac{M}{D} = \frac{M}{D_0 (1 - T_r)^{\frac{3}{2}}}$$

where M is the molecular weight. So, we have

$$V_0 = V(1 - T_n)^{3/0} \quad \dots (13)$$

V_0 and V are the zero volume and molecular volume respectively. Further, $0.27 V_0 = V_0$ (*idem*, *ibid.*, 1784), where V_c is the critical volume. Substituting in (13), we get

$$0.27 V_c = V(1 - T_n)^{3/0}.$$

At the boiling point, $T_n = 0.66$ (Guldberg, *loc. cit.*); hence one obtains

$$0.27 V_0 = V(1 - 0.66)^{3/0} \text{ or } V_0 = 2.68 V \quad \dots (14)$$

The thermodynamic equation of state is written as

$$p + \left(\frac{\partial E}{\partial V} \right)_T = T \left(\frac{\partial p}{\partial T} \right)_V \quad \dots (15)$$

the quantity $(\partial E/\partial V)_T$ being called the internal pressure (*vide* Brønsted, *loc. cit.*, p. 34).

If van der Waals equation of state

$$\left(p + \frac{a}{V^2} \right) (V - b) = RT \quad \dots (16)$$

is differentiated at constant volume, we get

$$\left(\frac{dp}{dT} \right)_V = \frac{R}{V - b}.$$

By combining with equation (16), we have

$$p + \frac{a}{V^2} = T \left(\frac{dp}{dT} \right)_V \quad \dots (17)$$

Hence,

$$\frac{a}{V^2} = \left(\frac{\partial E}{\partial V} \right)_T$$

(internal pressure) (*cf.* equations 15 & 17).

It follows from (16) that

$$\frac{a}{V^2} = \frac{RT}{V - b} - p = \frac{RT}{V - b}$$

neglecting the external pressure at the boiling point $p = 1$ atmos. in comparison with the internal pressure which is very large. Thus

$$\left(\frac{\partial E}{\partial V} \right)_T = \frac{RT}{V - b}.$$

It is known that the internal pressure (Hildebrand, "Solubility", Amer. Chem. Soc. Monograph Series, No. 17, 1936, p. 98, *et seq.*) is given over a limited range of temperature by the expression $\Delta E/V$. Thus we have at the boiling point,

$$\frac{\Delta E}{V} = \frac{RT_s}{V-b} \quad \dots (18)$$

Since the value of van der Waals' constant $b = V_c/3$, (18) can be written as

$$\frac{\Delta E}{V} = \frac{RT_s}{V - V_c/3} = \frac{RT_s}{(3V - V_c)/3}$$

Substituting for V_c according to (14), we have

$$\frac{\Delta E}{V} = \frac{3RT_s}{3V - 2 \cdot 68V} = 18 \cdot 75 T_s / V,$$

when R is taken as 2 calories, or $\frac{\Delta E}{T_s} = 18 \cdot 75$ calories/degree ... (19)

Since $\Delta H - RT_s = \Delta E$, we obtain $\frac{\Delta H}{T_s} = \frac{\Delta E}{T_s} + R = 18 \cdot 75$ calories/degree.

$$\text{or } \frac{\Delta H}{T_s} = 18 \cdot 75 + 2 = 20 \cdot 75 \text{ calories/degree.}$$

So, finally, the entropy of vaporisation is approximately given by the expression

$$\Delta S = \frac{\Delta H}{T_s} = 21 \text{ calories/degree.}$$

It may be pointed out that while deriving Trouton's rule by this method, only two empirical relations have been used, *viz.* Guldberg's rule (*loc. cit.*) and the ratio of

$$\frac{V_0}{V_c} = 0 \cdot 27 \text{ (Sugden, } loc. cit.)$$

Sugden's relation between density and temperature (12) is no longer considered as quite empirical since Macleod's equation (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1923, 19, 38) on which it was based has been derived by Fowler (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1937, A, 189, 227; *cf.* Butler, *loc. cit.*, p. 84).

C O N C L U S I O N

In very polar liquids such as water, alcohols, ammonia and other substances, there is a strong dipole attraction between molecules which would require an extra amount of energy for separation of the molecules into the vapour phase and hence these substances may not be expected to follow this rule. Further, a liquid that is not greatly expanded over its closely packed structure, such as mercury at ordinary temperature, hydrogen and helium which boil only a little above

absolute zero, are in a region where repulsive forces have an important part in balancing the attractive forces. It appears from the relation between internal pressure and molal volume (Hildebrand, *loc. cit.*) that elementary substances having a molal volume less than about 60 would not be anticipated to obey this rule.

Furthermore, as shown in (3), the values of Trouton's coefficients are dependent on the critical pressures which in turn are directly related to the internal pressures of liquids at their boiling points (Telang, unpublished work). From this and other foregoing considerations, it is tentatively proposed pending further work, that Trouton's coefficients should be compared not at equal vapour pressure *i.e.* the boiling points, but at temperatures at which substances have equal internal pressures.

DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
RAMNARAIN RUTIA COLLEGE,
BOMBAY.

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